

Towards integrating social and environmental sustainability in housing: conceptualisation, measurement frameworks, and indicators

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1. Introduction

The global housing crisis is an important social, environmental, and economic issue that is increasingly affecting more households, leading to housing deprivation. Housing is a “human right” (United Nations, 1948) and a primary physiological human need, underpinning progress towards improved quality of life, health, wellbeing, and life satisfaction. At the same time the climate emergency demands more ecological ways of living that vastly reduce energy consumption in order to achieve the European Commission’s goal of carbon neutrality by 2050 (European Commission, 2020). The current lack of adequate sustainable housing can be addressed by employing good practices throughout the design and construction of new housing, alongside drastic maintenance of existing buildings and neighbourhoods via regeneration, reuse and retrofit. The importance of involving communities in the decision-making process, by communicating lived experiences and realities, has been highlighted as a key factor to obtaining more equitable and socially just results (Dempsey et al., 2011). There is a demand for further empirical housing research to better understand the housing conditions of individuals and communities, subsequently improving the failings of housing.

2. Methodology

This research explores the meaning of sustainability in housing, to better understand the potential to address current inequalities. Social and environmental sustainability were explored under a broadly constructivist and critical paradigm, not only to challenge their separation, but also to recast the entire relationship between them. Sustainability was first analysed as a theoretical concept, followed by its practical application. In the first part, a literature review was conducted concerning social and environmental sustainability in housing as stand-alone, and integrated concepts. In the second part, Sustainable Assessment Tools (SATs) and their associated indicators were analysed. Framework indicators and conceptual definitions identified within the literature were then compared. This analysis indicates that future investigation into the successes and failures of housing case studies should be conducted through an integrated approach to sustainability, to identify areas for improvement.

3. Conceptualisation

Sustainability in the housing context is used as an umbrella term to incorporate the demands for affordable, inclusive, and environmentally responsible living environments. The most

common conceptualisation of sustainability follows the triple bottom line paradigm (Elkington, 1997), formed by social, environmental, and economic pillars. Other scholars have also added political, cultural, or institutional aspects (Littig & Grießler, 2005). However, sustainability is often used ambiguously or in a techno-managerial way (Mehmood & Parra, 2013) following a functionalist approach which silences existing conflicts and depoliticises the concept (Paidakaki & Lang, 2021). This reduces its meaning to ticking boxes on pre-defined frameworks that often prioritise environmental aspects (Berardi, 2012) because they are easier to measure (Manoochehri, 2016). Should sustainability be understood as part of a broader process following democratic values of decision-making, the co-production of housing can lead towards societal transformation.

Social sustainability proposes social relations within a city that improve the existing by opposing social inequalities, such as segregation and exclusion (Brindley, 2003). There are three main aspects of social impact within communities: social materiality (physical living conditions, physical health, and economic fairness), social equity (justice, human rights, and economic opportunities), and community life (community wellbeing and social networks). Further literature considers the relationship between social sustainability and the other two pillars through five main approaches (Edwards, 2019): a limiting constraint on the other dimensions (Boyer et al., 2016); a human developmental approach (Dempsey et al., 2011); a bridging approach between the others; a maintenance approach that preserves culture (Vallance et al., 2011); or an integrated, process-oriented approach (Edwards, 2019). Several critical points were identified to be examined during case study analysis: assessment of objective or subjective conditions, ontology of the 'community' and 'neighbourhood' groups, top-down or bottom-up indicators, and assessment of current or future oriented impact (Magee et al., 2012).

Environmental sustainability in housing revolves around reducing greenhouse gas emissions and energy consumption (European Commission, 2021). Energy efficiency can be achieved through two approaches: active and passive maintenance strategies affecting ventilation, heating, water, and electricity (Kubba, 2012b); and embodied energy savings. Passive maintenance design strategies include building shape and orientation, passive solar gain, daylighting, natural ventilation, thermal mass, and insulation to preserve warmth (Hannula, 2012; Kubba, 2012a), while active strategies use smart energy management systems to monitor and control mechanical systems, alongside energy production through renewable energy sources (RES). Energy savings through embodied energy can be achieved during production, transportation, material assemblage, and building technique (Hannula, 2012). Existing buildings have high embodied energy and therefore high environmental sustainability potential when integrated with passive and active maintenance techniques. Further, if residents' needs are integrated with care to avoid top-down decision-making that exacerbates disempowerment, social sustainability can be reached.

Separating environmental sustainability from the other pillars can lead to housing with especially low energy consumption. Such is the case with net zero energy buildings (NZEB) and energy positive buildings, which use on-site RES to produce as much, or more, energy than needed for building operation (D'Agostino et al., 2022; Kubba, 2012b). However, NZEBs rely on technical solutions that could create further social sustainability issues: increased upfront and maintenance costs, exacerbated inequalities, inaccessibility, and emotional distress (Lowe et al., 2018). Improving energy efficiency and housing quality while paying close attention to residents' needs can directly improve social sustainability through financial cost, health and wellbeing, and quality of life (URBED, 2022). To unify environmental and social sustainability, it is necessary to situate pragmatic environmental solutions within the critical paradigm.

4. Measurement

The shift towards sustainable development in recent decades has prompted the evolution of SATs to objectively measure sustainability. SATs are perceived as useful guides for decision-making during different phases of a project: planning, design, construction, maintenance, and end-of-life (Karji et al., 2019). Measurements can help assess housing and resident satisfaction, identify successes and failures in housing, and suggest further improvements. Comparative studies of SATs have been performed to better define key indicators and remove subjectivity from measurements (Thuvander et al., 2012; Al Waer & Sibley, 2005). Total quality assessment (TQA) systems aim to consider ecological, economic and social aspects, often including both qualitative and quantitative approaches for the varying criteria (Berardi, 2012). To test this aim, the four most widely used and researched TQA systems were chosen from the literature (Berardi, 2012; Karji et al., 2019; Orova & Reith, 2019; Thuvander et al., 2012) and analysed — BREEAM, LEED, CASBEE and DGNB — as well as the EU Level(s) Framework, launched in 2020 to homogenise housing sustainability measures (European Commission, 2021). The building scale and neighbourhood scale variation of each framework were analysed to broaden the scope of sustainability indicators.

5. Conclusion and discussion

The analysis found that the social dimensions of sustainability are only partially considered in existing measurement frameworks, which tend to favour building energy performance. As social sustainability is less profitable, it does not fit succinctly into existing market-orientated structures, and therefore sustainable technical housing infrastructure is favoured. However, housing sustainability must be approached holistically. To achieve this, the following recommendations are suggested: apply sustainability as a transformative process, rather than functioning as a checklist; take an embedded approach to incorporate community well-being, economic affordability, and energy efficiency; approach sustainability as a dynamic concept, in the same way that contexts, practices, and technologies evolve over time; be place-specific as homogenised frameworks are incompatible with the realities of diverse contexts. Finally, sustainability should be the result of a broader collaborative process between communities and institutions, so that residents have the opportunity to influence governing institutions towards policies for housing provision and adaptation aligned with their needs.

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